

Soundanism

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Biographical information

DissoNoiSex, comprised of Miguel Álvarez-Fernández, Stefan Kersten and Asia Piaścik, is a group of artists living and working in Berlin. Born in the late seventies, educated in Spain, Germany and Poland, and rooted in fields of expertise as diverse as musical composition, visual arts and computer science, the collective explores connections between music and sex through concepts such as controllability, dominance or repression (equally applied to dissonance, noise, or different sex-related practices). Their work has been presented in Spain (Menosuno Gallery, Madrid, and PING! Festival, Mallorca) and Germany (Takt Gallery, Berlin), and new projects are currently being developed for exhibitions in Czech Republic and Switzerland.

Description of Piece

Soundanism is an interactive sound installation exploring possible relationships between music, breathing, masturbation and sex.

The visitor, after putting on a helmet and a mask with a small electret microphone, takes part into a feedback system: he provokes all the sounds he perceives. The microphone picks up the sounds generated by his breathing, which are then digitally processed and transmitted through 14 small loudspeakers placed in the interior of the helmet. Additionally, information collected from the real-time analysis of the respiration is compared to the characteristics of thousands of sounds (connected in different degrees of obviousness with the idea of sex) that the visitor triggers and transforms, voluntarily or involuntarily, through his breathing.

Soundanism questions the notion of control in an interactive system. Located at the borderline between public and intimate, consciousness and dream, the work evades established categories such as installation, performance and instrument. It proposes an invitation: you can try to control and dominate the system, or relax and just breath...

